

CONSTITUTIVE MODELLING BASED ON MESO AND MICRO KINEMATICS FOR WOVEN AND STITCHED DRY FABRICS

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ABSTRACT

This work is aimed at modelling the deformation kinematics of both woven and stitched dry fabrics from a micro and mesoscopic perspective with the ultimate goal of developing constitutive models. The method behind the current approach is to analyse individually, distinct mechanisms of energy storage and dissipation for the deformation of dry fabrics and sum the resulting predictions to determine the overall force versus shear angle behaviour of the fabric. Certain energy dissipation mechanisms have been found to apply both to woven and stitched dry fabrics. One such mechanism can be identified as ‘crossover shear’. This mechanism was first treated in relation to the deformation of viscous woven textile composites. The crossover shear energy dissipation can be shown to be a direct result of the heterogeneous shear strain profile typically observed across the surface of sheared fabrics. In the first part of this paper, this crossover shear mechanism is adapted to dry fabrics, from viscous composites. Initially, the simpler case of a woven dry fabric is treated and discussed. Following this, the possibility of extending the model to the case of stitched dry fabrics is addressed. The second part of this paper focuses on the deformation kinematics of stitched fabrics. A meso-mechanical unit cell, based on the fabric’s stitch geometry is proposed and is used to model the shear behaviour of warp-knit non-crimp fabrics (NCFs). In particular, the model predicts the asymmetric draping behaviour observed in certain NCFs that is directly attributable to the fabric stitching. Finally, predictions from the crossover shear model, the unit cell stitch model and a compaction model are combined and the results are compared with experimental measurements.

Key words: Constitutive modelling, dry fabrics, draping

INTRODUCTION

Most engineered fabrics are not manufactured in the shape of the final component and are required to conform to the component shape through draping. Knowledge of the final draped pattern of a dry fabric can inform several manufacturing factors. These include prediction of the optimum undraped shape of the flat blank prior to draping and of the flow of resin through the fabric at the injection stage of resin transfer moulding. Equally important, accurate knowledge of final fibre orientation is essential for a complete structural analysis. For engineered fabrics based on high modulus fibres, biaxial fabrics tend to conform to a given geometry with double curvature, primarily through in-plane trellis shearing. This enables the fabric to achieve the required local changes in surface area without inducing fabric wrinkles. Consequently, it is necessary to understand the fabric’s shear compliance, in order to model the draping process accurately. Given the appropriate material behaviour, either through a constitutive equation or otherwise through experimentally produced look-up tables, finite element drape simulations [1] can produce accurate predictions. However, these simulations are often computationally expensive and generally require extensive operator experience before the software can be employed confidently. This makes finite element simulations unsuitable for early design iterations. At the other extreme of numerical simulation techniques, the pin-jointed net (PJN) method [2] can produce results quickly and requires only basic user training. However, while this method implicitly incorporates the kinematic constraint of fibre

inextensibility it completely ignores the shear behaviour of the material. The absence of material behaviour in basic PJN simulations is particularly evident when attempting to simulate the draping of non-crimp fabrics (NCFs), since NCFs often produce asymmetric draping patterns as a result of their asymmetric shear compliances.

A modified version of the PJN technique has since been proposed [2] based on an energy minimisation argument. The method behind the modified PJN technique is based on optimisation of the simulations' 'generator paths', the paths of two fibres passing over the component for which the intersection angle between the paths is specified and from which the kinematic constraint of fibre inextensibility allows the rest of the draping pattern to be calculated. This modified PJN energy minimisation technique incorporates the material's shear behaviour, albeit in a simple manner, and thus provides a numerical simulation option lying somewhere between the finite element and basic PJN methods, both in terms of computation time and accuracy. Fundamental to the modified PJN technique is knowledge of the fabric's shear compliance. Currently, this requires experiments. A desirable goal is to eliminate this requirement so that any material drape can be modelled quickly without the need for difficult, time-consuming and expensive material characterisation experiments. With this in mind, meso- and micro-mechanical models have been developed that can predict the fabric's shear behaviour, using readily supplied material properties, such as fibre volume fraction and, in the case of NCFs, the stitch geometry.

CROSSOVER SHEARING IN WOVEN FABRICS

Crossover shear energy dissipation has been discussed previously with regard to viscous textile composites [3]. In this section, a method of determining the energy dissipation due to shearing between crossovers in a dry fabric is outlined. The main difference is that for viscous composites, the energy dissipation is related to the instantaneous rate of shearing in the film of viscous matrix fluid separating crossovers. For dry fabrics, crossovers are considered to be in direct contact and therefore energy dissipation is related to relative displacement rather than the rate of relative displacement. This point is elaborated in the following analysis, in which the mechanism of crossover shear energy dissipation is most conveniently explained in terms of the fabric architecture of woven fabrics rather than NCFs. Nevertheless, the crossover shearing mechanism is also shown to be relevant to energy dissipation in NCFs and the possibility of applying the model to NCFs is discussed.

Figure 1 3-harness satin weave glass fibre fabric, (a) black line marked in ink before shear (b) after 40 degrees of shear the black line is clearly broken (c) Shear of two tows and separating inter-tow region. Continuous-line shows local displacement profile across tow and inter-tow regions, dashed-line shows average displacement profile across the fabric sheet.

During shear, the in-plane shear rate of tows is rarely as high as the overall in-plane shear rate across the composite sheet [3,4]. This produces a non-uniform displacement profile across the fabric, as shown in Figure 1 (b). If the strain profile were uniform then the straight line marked on the fabric in Figure 1(a) would remain straight following shear. The subsequent idealised strain profile due to this heterogeneous shear across the fabric is illustrated in Figure 1 (c). The heterogeneous shear profile across the sample implies relative shear between tow crossovers. In [3] the relative 2-D kinematics occurring between crossovers was derived as

$$\bar{v}_{rel} = \{(\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega)(1 - \sin \theta)Y\} \hat{i} + \{(\omega - \dot{\gamma}_t)(1 - \sin \theta)X\} \hat{j} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{v}_{rel} is the relative velocity field between the crossovers, $\dot{\gamma}_t$ is the in-plane shear strain rate in both sets of tows and in the following calculation is considered constant in time, ω is the relative angular shear rate of the two sets of tows, θ is the material shear angle and X, Y are the position co-ordinates, with the origin at the centre of the crossover. Figure 2 illustrates the material shear angle, θ , the co-ordinate system and also some useful lengths used in the subsequent analysis of the crossover kinematics. Eq. (1) suggests that if $\dot{\gamma}_t \neq \omega$ then there is relative motion between crossovers. Eq. (1) can be used to find the path-line of a given initial position as a function of time, t . Thus, it can be shown that for constant ω , $\theta = \omega t$ and

$$\frac{dX}{dt} = X(\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega)^2 \left\{ \left(t + \frac{\cos \theta}{\omega} \right) (\sin \theta - 1) \right\} - C_1 (\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega) (\sin \theta - 1), \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{dY}{dt} = Y(\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega)^2 \left\{ \left(t + \frac{\cos \theta}{\omega} \right) (\sin \theta - 1) \right\} + C_2 (\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega) (\sin \theta - 1) \quad (3)$$

Figure 2 Kinematics and geometry of crossover area. θ is the material shear angle, w is the side-length of the crossover, d is the diagonal displacement of one corner of the material with respect to the opposite corner and F is an the axial force (directed along the long diagonal axis) required to induce the material deformation. The co-ordinate system is indicated in the diagram.

where the constants C_1 and C_2 depend on the initial position of the point, i.e. when $t = 0$, $X(0) = X_o$ and $Y(0) = Y_o$. Thus,

$$C_1 = Y_o + \frac{(\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega)}{\omega} X_o \quad (4)$$

$$C_2 = X_o - \frac{(\dot{\gamma}_t - \omega)}{\omega} Y_o \quad (5)$$

The energy dissipation due to friction between crossovers is calculated numerically. The method involves dividing the crossover area into discrete elements (see Figure 3) numbered 1 to i . Initial positions of the centres of the elements are spaced according to a square grid pattern. Eq. (2) and (3) are both non-separable first order differential equations. Thus, to determine $X(t)$ and $Y(t)$ as a function of time, the Runge-Kutta technique is employed [4], where the time steps, t_j , are numbered 1 to j . The distance increment, l_i , of each element's path-line, between times t_j and t_{j+1} , is calculated. If the path-line of a given element meets the condition that it is inside the area of the crossover at time t_j and remains within the new crossover area at time t_{j+1} , then the distance increment of the path-line, l_i , is used in the subsequent energy calculation. This condition is illustrated in Figure 3, which shows how the path-lines of certain elements enter while others leave the crossover area during the course of the simulation. In Figure 3 (b) two path-lines are circled, the black line circles a path-line about to leave the crossover area, while the grey line circles a path-line that has entered the crossover area during the course of the simulation. In Figure 3 (c) the initial position of the path-line has left the crossover area (circled) even though the current position of the path-line remains inside the area. Consequently, this path-line is included in the energy calculation at the time step illustrated.

Figure 3 Discretised crossover shown at shear angles of (a) 0° (b) 20° and (c) 40° . The points indicate the initial position of the path-line inside the crossover area while the lines indicate the subsequent paths of the path-lines, in this calculation $\dot{\gamma}_t = 0.5\omega$.

The area of each element, $A(t_j)$, is defined as the crossover area at time, t_j , divided by the number of elements inside the area at time t_j . Energy dissipation is calculated by multiplying the distance increment of each path-line, l_i , that meets the condition described above, by the element area, $A(t_j)$, the normal pressure between crossovers, $P(t_j)$, and the coefficient of dynamic friction, μ . This calculation is summed over all the elements to find the energy dissipation, $U_X(t_j)$, due to friction at the crossovers during a given time increment. Thus,

$$U_{X_j} = P_j A_j \mu \sum_i l_i \quad (6)$$

where the j subscript indicates the value of the variable at time t_j . Using Figure 2, this energy can be equated with the work required to displace the top corner of the crossover by a distance, $d(t_j)$ in the time increment t_j to t_{j+1} . For sufficiently small time increments the axial force, $F(t_j)$, can be considered constant and is found by dividing the energy U_{X_j} by the distance increment d_j . Axial force is then converted to the shear force simply by dividing by $2\cos(\pi/4 - \theta_j/2)$.

Figure 4 Effect of side length on shear force produced by crossover shear, calculated using arbitrary parameters, $\mu = 0.3$, $P_j = 3000 \text{ Nm}^{-2}$, $\dot{\gamma} = 0.5\omega$. The shear force per unit length increases linearly with the side length of the crossover. Oscillations in the predicted shear force result from the spatial discretisation method used in the numerical code

It is interesting to examine the effect of the size of the crossover on the shear force per unit length of the fabric. For the purposes of this calculation the pressure acting on the surface of the crossover, P_j , was taken to be constant with increasing shear angle (see figure caption). Convergence was obtained using 40 elements. The only parameter varied between calculations was the side length of the crossover. Figure 4 shows that for a constant pressure, the crossover contribution to the shear force decreases with increasing shear angle and that the shear force is directly proportional to the side length of the crossover. For woven fabrics this length dependence is a minor point since the size of the crossovers is well defined by the width of the woven tows. However, this is not the case for NCFs. In the next section, the effect of crossover shear on NCFs is considered and preliminary quantitative predictions are made and combined with a unit cell model of the stitch geometry.

CROSSOVER SHEARING IN NON-CRIMP FABRICS

The subject of crossover shearing is continued in this section with respect to NCFs. Many NCFs comprise two layers of unidirectional fibres, initially orientated at 90° to each other and stitched together. Each layer of the fabric is originally manufactured using bundles of fibres, or tows, laid in parallel. These tows are then pierced by the fabric stitch. Consequently, the stitch appears to define the new tows in the fabric. However, the actual situation is often more complicated since fibres within one ‘apparent’ tow can move across an apparent tow boundary. The degree to which fibres move across apparent tow boundaries is related to the alignment between fibre orientation and stitch pattern. A consequence of this is that the dimensions of the crossovers may span a relatively broad range of length scales and in general will be of initially rectangular form of various length/width aspect ratios rather than square.

To investigate the effect of crossover shearing on NCFs, experimental data have been measured for a tricot stitch warp knit NCF E-glass fabric of class, FGE 106, with an areal density of 936g/m^2 . The tows are initially orientated at $\pm 45^\circ$ to the stitch, with initial stitch lengths $c_o = 2.5\text{mm}$ and $d_o = 4.86\text{mm}$ and stitch spacing $h_o = 4.17\text{mm}$ (see Figure 5). The fabric thickness T is taken to be 2mm , and the stitch modulus is taken as 2GPa . $A_s = 0.1\text{mm}$ where A_s is the effective cross-sectional area of the stitch. The

stitch geometry is shown in Figure 5. Photographs of both sides of the fabric were recorded before and after positive and negative shear (see Figure 6).

Figure 5 One example of a unit cell, left, for a $\pm 45^\circ$ tricot warp knit NCF. The upper layer of tows run vertically (solids grey lines), the bottom layer run horizontally (dashed grey lines). The stitch (black lines), runs over the tows (d , black solid line), pierces through the fabric thickness (T) and then runs under the tows (c , black dashed line).

Image analysis of the form of the shear strain profile, indicated by the marked line in Figure 6 on both sides of the fabric, has provided statistical data on the length scale and shape of the crossovers, along with the shear angle in the tows, χ , versus fabric shear angle, θ . Results shown in Figure 7 show wide distributions of tow width on both surfaces of the fabric following positive and negative shear. Tow shear angle measurements in Figure 8 also indicate a large amount of scatter. Future work will involve using such statistical data to predict variability in the crossover shear force using, for example, the Monte Carlo method. For the purposes of this paper just the average values of the data are used. Thus, the average crossover side length was calculated to be 0.00187 m and the average tow shear rate, $\dot{\gamma}$, was estimated to be about 0.3ω .

Figure 6 A continuous black line was marked across both sides of the fabric surface and photographed following shear. Diagonal and chain refer to the stitch pattern as seen on the two surfaces of the fabric (a) diagonal side, unsheared, (b) chain side, unsheared, (c) diagonal side, positive shear, (d) chain side, positive shear, (e) diagonal side, negative shear and (f) chain side, negative shear. Units of the ruler shown in the pictures are measured in cm.

In the final section of this paper, crossover predictions based on average length scale and tow shear rate measurements are made and combined with predictions of the stitch and compaction models described in the following sections.

Figure 7 Statistical data measured from image analysis (a) tow width on diagonal side, positive shear 57 measurements, negative shear 42 measurements (b) tow width on chain side, positive shear 66 measurements, negative shear 58 measurements.

Figure 8 Tow shear angle, χ , versus fabric shear angle, θ . Data collected following both positive and negative shear (see legend). Each point is an average of at least 40 measurements. Black line indicates homogeneous shear and grey line indicates a linear fit with $\chi = 0.3\theta$ to the data.

UNIT CELL STITCH MODEL

For NCFs the stitch contributes a significant proportion of the energy involved in shearing the fabric and in many cases can induce asymmetric shear behaviour [6]. Using a geometric unit-cell stitch model, various energy storage/dissipation mechanisms can be analysed. Mechanisms considered here include: stitch tension and inter-stitch friction. Consider the unit tricot stitch illustrated in Figure 5. Shear deformation requires that sections of the stitch, not parallel to the tow direction must change dimensions. The variation of c and d with shear angle can be determined from geometric constraints. Thus,

$$c(\theta) = \sqrt{2}c_0 \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\theta}{2}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$d(\theta) = \sqrt{2c_0^2 \cos^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\theta}{2}\right) + 2h_0^2 \sin^2\left(\frac{\pi}{4} - \frac{\theta}{2}\right)} \quad (8)$$

To determine the variation of the through-thickness stitch segments, T , the relationship between the stitch tension and tow compaction is required. As a first approximation, T is assumed constant with respect to shear angle [2].

Figure 9 An enlarged view of a stitch crossover. At the point at which the stitch passes through the fabric, it is constrained by the loop from a previous stitch.

This is a reasonable assumption for dry fabrics with low initial fibre volume fraction, as the thickness variation only becomes relevant at high shear angles, where compaction forces dominate. Presuming the stitch passes freely through the stitch crossovers (illustrated in Figure 9), the tension in the stitch can be considered constant through the entire length. Summing the overall length of the c , d and T sections gives its overall stitch length, L , in terms of shear angle. From this, the strain in the stitch ε_s , where the subscript, s , indicates that variables are related to the stitch, can be determined as

$$\varepsilon_s = \frac{L(\theta) - L_o}{L_o} = \frac{\Delta L}{L_o} \quad (9)$$

where L_o is the unstressed stitch length. The stitch is manufactured under a given strain, and so L_o does not necessarily correspond to L when $\theta = 0$, the stitch length at zero shear. The stitching used in the material shows a fairly linear stress-strain relationship so that, prior to failure stitch stress, σ_s , is related to stitch strain as $\sigma_s = E_s \varepsilon_s$. In terms of stitch tension, $S_s = A_s \sigma_s$, the energy due to stitch extension, U_s , is determined by integrating the stitch tension with respect to stitch length to find

$$U_s = \frac{E_s A_s}{2L_o} (\Delta L)^2 \quad (10)$$

Eq. (10) applies for tension only, as the stitch shows virtually no compressive stiffness. This energy can be normalised with respect to the surface area of the unit cell, $2c_0h_0$, and added to the energy contributions from the other shear mechanisms. For a shear test in which the whole fabric is in constant, pure shear, this energy can be differentiated with respect to shear angle to produce an overall shear torque per unit length, τ , from which the shear force per unit length due to stitch extension can be calculated by dividing by $\cos\theta$. Experimental observations confirm that the stitching does move through the fabric during shear, as assumed in the above analysis. A simple model for approximating the frictional resistance to stitch movement is proposed. Referring to Figure 9, the stitching is taken to be stationary at the apex of the loop as this is a point of symmetry with respect to both stitch tension and geometry. Considering the loop section of the stitch, c in Eq. (1), and the diagonal section of the stitch, d in Eq. (2), if the rate of strain imposed in these is not equal then the corresponding unequal tension would cause thread to pass from one to the other. Approximating the lateral force at the point of contact to the tension in the stitch, the frictional resistance, F_f is given as $F_f = \mu_s S_s$ where μ_s is the dynamic friction of stitch on stitch movement. This force can be integrated with respect to distance and multiplied by the number of contact points in the unit cell (four) to find the energy dissipation due to stitch-stitch friction, U_f . This can subsequently be combined with the other energy dissipation/storage mechanisms to find the total shear force of the fabric.

COMPACTION MODEL

For convenience the Cai and Gutowski model [7] for compaction of lubricated fabrics, as adapted by McBride [8] for dry aligned E-glass tows, has been used. Thus, given the following variation of volume fraction with shear angle (assuming constant thickness),

$$V_f(\theta_s) = V_f(0) / \cos \theta \quad (11)$$

this equation is considered valid until V_f approaches the maximum volume fraction of 85 percent [8] at about $\theta = 60^\circ$. Assuming zero axial strain, compaction stress lateral to the fibre direction, σ_c , can be derived as

$$\sigma_c = \frac{e_b F_{11}}{F_{bb} F_{11} - F_{b1}^2} \quad (12)$$

where e_b is the applied lateral strain, and the constants are evaluated as suggested by McBride for dry E-glass. The applied lateral strain can be expressed in terms of fibre volume fraction, which in turn can be related to the shear angle. This stress can be integrated to produce an energy term, U_c , the energy storage/dissipation due to compaction. As indicated earlier, this can be added to the other energy contributions to find the total energy storage/dissipation. Conveniently, σ_b can also be used to provide an estimate of the pressure parameter in the crossover model, P_j in Eq. (6).

RESULTS

In this section the results of crossover, stitch and compaction models are combined to produce a total shear force prediction that is compared against experimental results. Experiments were performed on the same NCF as described earlier in this paper. The separate normalised force contributions from each mechanism are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10 Four separate contributions to the total normalised shear force of the stitch fabric.

Figure 10 suggests that for a constant thickness assumption, the stitch tension provides the dominant contribution to the total shear force at low θ , with stitch friction providing the next largest contribution. At higher θ the compaction contribution becomes the most important mechanism. The crossover contribution appears to be negligible until relatively high values of θ . The sudden increase of this contribution can be explained by the sharply increasing normal pressure, P_j , predicted by Eq (11) and (12), as the fabric is compressed towards its maximum possible fibre volume fraction. In reality, a coupling between stitch tension and crossover force should be expected and may result in a larger contribution from the crossover force at low θ . The formulation of this coupling is a possible future step in the model development. Combined model predictions are compared against experimental data in Figure 11. The fabric was tested using a picture frame test rig [3]. In this test, four sides of a cruciform specimen are clamped such that the clamping edges are parallel and perpendicular to the tows. The sides of the rig are pin-jointed so that when diagonally opposite corners are extended, the rig subjects the entire specimen to uniform trellis shear. Referring to Figure 11, the fabric produces a greater shear resistance in one shear direction than in the opposite sense, a behaviour typically observed for stitched fabrics. The model predicts this asymmetric behaviour and shear force values of similar to the measured behaviour.

Discrepancies can be attributed, at least in part, to possible error in the measured force. Large variability in fabric shear data is common during picture frame testing. A second reason may lie in the assumed geometry of the unit cell stitch model. Observations show at least some degree of stitch reorganisation during shear that may serve to relax the amount of stitch extension.

Figure 11 Combined model predictions plus experimental data produced by picture frame tests.

CONCLUSIONS

Various energy dissipation/storage mechanisms have been analysed for dry fabrics. These include crossover shear, stitch tension, stitch friction and fabric compaction. The combined model results are promising. The model reproduces the asymmetric shear behaviour measured for many stitched fabrics and shear force predictions show close correlation with experimental results. Future work will include refinement of the model and the effects of statistical variations in the tow kinematics and stitch pattern, on the shear force of the fabric will be investigated. A longer-term goal will be to predict these statistical variations through analysis of the stitch/fibre interaction and the fabric manufacture process.

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